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Use case report

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1. Executive Summary

The present document is a deliverable (D2.6) of the B1MGplus project, entitled Use Case Report. The Use Cases (hereafter the 'UC') refers to five thematic areas within genomic medicine which were identified as high-priority topics by the 1+MG community in the early stages of the 1+MG initiative. As a consequence, these five 1+MG UCs have been an integral component of the implementation efforts for several years, with each of the five UCs having a dedicated 1+MG WG associated with it.

The purpose of this document is to revisit the five 1+MG UCs within the domain of genomic medicine, in order to assess the extent to which the evolving 1+MG infrastructure and its governance framework continue to meet the needs of the UCs and to contribute to a value proposition for both the user community and decision makers. A broader objective of this exercise is to contribute to the sustainability of the forthcoming Genome EDIC by reflecting on the utility of the Genome EDIC's offering to the target community. The work reported in the present deliverable is part of WP2 ("Genome EDIC Establishment") activities of the B1MGplus project.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

Outcome 1		Contributed
Supporting the Genome EDIC WG and the 1+MG Member States on the establishment of the EDIC by carrying out the field work required to generate high quality landscape and scoping documents necessary for the compliance framework beyond the legal creation of an EDIC. These documents will drive EDIC to become operational and offer compliant access to health and genomic data, covering legal, policy, quality and security aspects of data provision.	1. A record of processing activities that captures the legitimacy of EDIC and the corresponding safeguards	No
	2. A number of documents that can be fed back to the GDI Pillar I and/or the EDIC for discussion and/or adoption to provide legal tools and policies to govern the operations for suitable and specific safeguards to ensure the protection of the rights and freedoms of the data subjects whose data are included in the EDIC for secondary use.	No
	3. A framework that can guide the implementation of national IT infrastructure to ensure the quality and the security of workflows, tools and platforms.	No
Outcome 2		Contributed
WP2 will analyse the EHDS Regulation and will seek close exchange with relevant projects and stakeholders to investigate the conditions for a participation in the	1. An analysis of the model how the EDIC could join the EHDS, its relationship with the various stakeholders	No

HealthData@EU infrastructure, to give recommendations on the alignment of its policies, tools, security measures and IT framework with the requirements of the EHDS.	and the conditions and opportunities of such participation	
	2. Information on the practical consequences of the participation in the HealthData@EU infrastructure	No
	3. Engaging public health professionals, and policy makers, in the discussion of benefits and challenges of adopting genomics in healthcare systems for clinical practice and public health policies	Yes
	4. Documenting the implementation of genomic medicine practices in national healthcare systems	No
	5. Promoting the awareness, literacy level and education of citizens on genomic medicine across Europe.	No
Outcome 3		Contributed
WP3 will provide a framework of reference for genomics in healthcare that supports the decision making process, facilitating the definition of mid and long term targets and the path for genomics implementation, incorporating the feedback received from B1MG and the 1+MG experts.	1. Mapping of gaps, challenges, unmet needs and solutions from the perspective of public health and healthcare professionals, healthcare systems and national genomic healthcare implementation programmes	No
	2. Recommendations for the EDIC on the uptake and implementation of genomics for healthcare and public health	Yes
	3. A citizen's hub for dissemination of genomic medicine, promoting citizens and patients awareness, literacy and trust	No
Outcome 4		Contributed
The project will map existing studies on health economy and health technology assessments related to whole genome sequencing and other comprehensive genetic tests in healthcare. Building on the collected best practices, and together with experts in the field, the project will develop decision trees to be tested in national settings to guide decision making related to genomics in healthcare. The long term impact of the work is the scoping of a project on economic impact of genomic medicine in healthcare to	1. Overview of literature and existing studies on health economy and health technology assessments related to WGS and other comprehensive genetic tests in healthcare	No

support future prioritisation in healthcare, policy makers and decisions on investment in genomic medicine.	2. Decision trees tested in national settings	No
	3. Scoping of a project on economic impact of genomic medicine in healthcare	No
Outcome 5		Contributed
Enhancing the 1+MG MLM for the implementation of genomics medicine in healthcare systems with updated domains and indicators, promoting its use and benchmarking by more healthcare systems. This will provide an homogeneous assessment framework that will foster the alignment of optimisation aims in healthcare systems across Europe, closing gaps, reducing asymmetries and ensuring a path towards equity of access to personalised medicine for all Europeans.	1. Updated 1+MG MLM incorporating novel dimensions aligned with emerging developments in genomic medicine	Yes
	2. Benchmarking of the MLM by healthcare systems across europe	Yes
Outcome 6		Contributed
Expand the 1+MG Framework to fully define the 1+MG minimal metadata model, data standards, ontologies and quality criteria providing accessibility and maintenance, ensuring continuous alignment and support of 1+MG data use for research, innovation and policy making.	1. Phenotype data model	Yes
	2. Genotype data model	Yes
	3. Terms of use/ELSI metadata	No
	4. Software quality indicators for components to be incorporated into the 1+MG journey.	Yes
	5. Data/metadata provenance models	Yes

3. Introduction

3.1. Europe’s 1+ Million Genomes Initiative

The 1+ Million Genomes (1+MG) Initiative is a flagship European undertaking in genomic medicine. It was created to enable secure cross-border access to genomic and clinical data for healthcare providers, researchers, and policymakers. Its overarching goal is to create a federated ecosystem in which genomic data can be accessed and analysed across Europe.¹ The 1+MG Initiative was launched in April 2018 through a political Declaration signed, thus far, by 27 countries, which includes 25 EU Member States, Norway and the United Kingdom. The initiative seeks to enable cross-border access to, and reuse of, at least one million sequenced genomes and associated health data in a harmonised fashion.²

The motivation behind the 1+MG Initiative was to address several structural challenges facing the European genomics landscape. The most notable challenges stemmed from the fragmentation of legal frameworks for data sharing, including the absence of any legislation, infrastructure, data standards and data resources across Member States. This fragmentation has been often perceived as a key hindering factor placing Europe at a competitive disadvantage compared to large-scale genomic initiatives in other parts of the world, notably the United States and China.³

An additional and closely related reason for the establishment of the 1+MG Initiative was the need for genomic and phenotypic data **discovery at scale**. Institutional or national databases might lack the size to identify a sufficient number of patients with rare genetic variants or to validate associations among genetic variation, phenotypic traits, and clinical outcomes. By combining genomes and accompanying health data across multiple countries into a larger European 1+MG “virtual cohort”, researchers, clinical geneticists, and health policy-makers could substantially overcome these limitations, advancing genomics-informed personalised disease prevention, diagnosis, and treatment. The 1+MG initiative brings Europe closer to personalised medicine by enabling tailored use of phenotypic and genotypic data to deliver prevention and treatment adapted to each individual.

¹ For the overview of the initiative, see 1+ Million Genomes Framework. *1+MG Framework*. Accessed November 11, 2025, from <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu>; European Commission. *European '1+ Million Genomes' initiative*. Shaping Europe's Digital Future. Accessed November 11, 2025, from <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/1-million-genomes>.

² For the news of the declaration see, **European Commission** (2018, April 10). *EU countries will cooperate in linking genomic databases across borders* [News article]. Shaping Europe's Digital Future. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/eu-countries-will-cooperate-linking-genomic-databases-across-borders>.

³ European Commission (2024) 137 final. Accessed November 11, 2025 https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/47554adc-dffc-411b-8cd6-b52417514cb3_en; Romina Royo, Eva Garcia, Irene Schlünder, Christina Hilmarsen, Mette Kielsholm Thomsen, Emilie Cauët, Simon Kok Jensen, Simona Giardina, Aline Hebrant, Gordana Raicevic Toungouz, Marc Van Den Bulcke, Juan Arenas, Christian Fynbo Christiansen, Eivind Hovig, Petr Holub, Alfonso Valencia, Salvador Capella-Gutierrez, Genomic data sharing in research across Europe: legal challenges and upcoming opportunities within the European Health Data Space, *European Journal of Public Health*, Volume 35, Issue Supplement_3, September 2025, Pages iii25–iii31, <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/ckaf070>

Equally important is the **maximisation of prior public investments**. Before the 1+MG Initiative, European countries had already dedicated substantial funding to genome sequencing efforts, often accompanied by investments in the data infrastructures to integrate the generated data into biobanks and healthcare systems. However, these valuable assets often remained beyond the reach of the researchers, medical professionals, and health policy-makers - across hospitals, regions, nationally, and in other countries. To counter redundancy and avoid duplication of the efforts across Europe, the 1+MG Initiative aims to leverage the existing data collections and genomic infrastructures through an integrated cross-border network architecture.

As such, the 1+MG initiative is aligned with the EU's broader health and data policy frameworks which includes the Digital Transformation of Health and Care agenda, the European Health Data Space, Europe's Beating Cancer Plan, the European Data Strategy, and the European Open Science Cloud. As then-Commissioner for Digital Economy and Society Mariya Gabriel emphasized at launch, cross-border interoperability and secure access to genomic and related health data are fundamental to ensuring that Europe remains at the forefront of health innovation and research.⁴

At the technical core of 1+MG lies a federated, secure data infrastructure. Under this model, genomic and phenotypic data remain physically stored in nationally managed storage facilities connected to secure processing environments, in which authorised users can perform their analysis. This approach maintains national data sovereignty while enabling European-scale cross-border collaboration through common standards and secure application programming interfaces (APIs). The infrastructure is intended to support all key functionalities throughout the data use lifecycle: data inclusion (i.e., depositing and storing data on the local/national nodes), data discovery by prospective users, access management and – where access is granted to the user - data analysis in a secure processing environment - and eventually doing so in a federated manner across several countries.

3.2. 1+MG Governance Structure and Implementation Roadmap

The 1+MG initiative was conceived as a unifying framework to allow cross-border access to data, harmonise standards and data governance and build the scale necessary for Europe to achieve global leadership in genomic medicine. To achieve these aims, the Signatory Member States defined four overarching objectives.⁵ **First**, to establish a secure,

⁴ Intel. (April 19, 2018). *Europe, AI, and genomics – Big topics discussed at Digital Day 2018* [Blog post]. Intel Community. <https://community.intel.com/t5/Blogs/Intel/Policy-Intel/Europe-AI-and-Genomics-Big-Topics-Discussed-at-Digital-Day-2018/post/1333042>

⁵ Objectives are outlined in the *Declaration of Cooperation: Towards access to at least 1 million sequenced genomes in the European Union by 2022*. Accessed December 15, 2025, from

interoperable, and federated technical infrastructure across the European Union.⁶ **Second**, to develop a coordinated data governance framework necessary to facilitate Europe-wide large-scale processing of health and related data in compliance with the applicable data protection legal framework.⁷ **Third**, to promote the use of open standards and data management systems to ensure interoperability of genomic and other health data with a view to enhance research on personalised medicine and genetic diseases. **Fourth**, to promote public and policy awareness of genomics, ensuring that the technology becomes integrated into routine healthcare delivery.⁸

The initiative's governance structure ensures coherence among political commitment, expert-led implementation, and national execution.

3.2.1. Strategic and Operational Coordination

At the strategic level, the 1+MG Initiative is supported by the 1+MG Group, established by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology (DG CNECT). It brings together national authorities responsible for health policy and research. Meeting up to four times annually, the Group coordinates policy direction, endorses technical deliverables, and advises the Commission on relevant regulatory developments.

Operational execution occurs through twelve specialized Working Groups (WGs).⁹ Each 1+MG WG addresses a distinct matter: governance and coordination, ELSI, data quality and standards, infrastructure, interoperability, healthcare implementation, analytics, and 1+MG UCs covering five therapeutic areas: rare diseases, cancer, common complex diseases (including pharmacogenomics), infectious diseases, and population genomics.¹⁰ These WGs define specifications, guidelines, and implementation blueprints underpinning the 1+MG Framework.

National Mirror Groups: At national level, National Mirror Groups (NMGs) replicate the WG structure. They bring together policymakers, technical experts, clinicians, patient representatives, and industry stakeholders. NMGs ensure national alignment with the European framework, coordinate infrastructure deployment, manage data access and

https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=50964. See also at **1+ Million Genomes Framework**. *1+MG Framework*. Accessed November 11, 2025, from <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu>.

⁶ **1+ Million Genomes Framework**. *Technical infrastructure*. Accessed November 11, 2025, from <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/technical-infrastructure>.

⁷ **1+ Million Genomes Framework**. *Legal, ethics and governance*. Accessed November 11, 2025, from <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/governance-elsi>.

⁸ **1+ Million Genomes Framework**. *Implementation of genomics into healthcare*. Accessed November 11, 2025, from <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/genomics-into-healthcare>.

⁹ European Commission. *European '1+ Million Genomes' initiative*. Shaping Europe's Digital Future. Accessed November 11, 2025, from <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/1-million-genomes>.

¹⁰ The list of the use cases corresponding to the five therapeutic areas is accurate as of mid-2025.

quality, and facilitate dialogue among relevant actors. They also contribute feedback to European-level working groups to maintain coherence between national and EU actions.¹¹

3.2.2. European project supporting the Implementation of 1+MG

The practical implementation of the 1+MG vision has been supported by dedicated multicountry projects. These projects are structured as international consortia consisting of diverse institutional partners mainly from academia and the public sector. The partners bring complementary expertise to the consortia, spanning the domains of genetics, bioinformatics, information technology, ethical and legal aspects of genomic data governance, as well as public health and policy-making.

The first consortium-based project supporting the 1+MG implementation was Beyond 1 Million Genomes (B1MG). During its course (2020-2023), B1MG built upon, and complemented the work of 1+MG WGs, crystallising a more detailed implementation blueprint, with an extensive set of guidelines, technical specifications, and governance requirements. This effort was followed by Genomic Data Infrastructures (GDI), which commenced in November 2022 with the aim of translating the B1MG blueprint into functional infrastructural components able to meet user needs in a cross-border setting. Another important objective of the GDI project has been to formalise the governance model of the 1+MG ecosystem, including designating the legal entity tasked with operationalising the 1+MG vision based on the B1MG blueprint, defining the entity's mandate, and deciding on its governance structure. As of November 2025, the GDI consortium has made significant progress towards this objective: it has endorsed the establishment of a dedicated 1+MG European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC), a novel form of specialised multi-country legal entity created by Member States. An EDIC was deemed the most suitable option for carrying out the entity's mission.¹² Subsequently, Luxembourg was nominated as the country to host the forthcoming Genome EDIC, with the voting among GDI members on this matter currently ongoing. Before the conclusion of the GDI project it is expected that additional decisions will be made regarding the scope and specific tasks of the forthcoming Genome EDIC.

To further complement and support the aforementioned 1+MG Implementation efforts, particularly those of the B1MG project and the governance decisions made by the GDI consortium, a new project was launched in February 2025. The project, entitled "Beyond 1 Million Genomes plus" (B1MGplus), is expected to run until the end of January 2028,

¹¹ **1+ Million Genomes Framework. National implementation.** Accessed November 11, 2025, from <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/national-implementation>

¹² The European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) consortium *Country representatives vote on interim and long-term sustainability* Accessed 22 November 2025 <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/news/interim-and-long-term-sustainability>

spanning 3 years.¹³ B1MGplus is supporting the sustainability of the forthcoming Genome EDIC and the cross-border data infrastructure under its governance.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1. 1+MG Use Case workshops

As noted previously, during the early phases of the 1+MG Initiative, 1+MG UCs were identified as high-priority areas for the Initiative. Subsequently, the UCs were formally incorporated into the structure of the Initiative as dedicated 1+MG WGs. In total, there are five UCs that focus on a distinct medical/therapeutic area within genomic medicine, namely Rare Diseases, Cancer, Common Complex Diseases (including pharmacogenomics), Infectious Diseases, and Population Genomics.

The 1+MG WGs dedicated to these five UCs bring together experts with specialised clinical and research expertise in their respective fields of genomic medicine. Collectively, the 1+MG UC expert groups have been contributing the knowledge and insights that have helped shape the 1+MG Initiative's offering to the target community. With the imminent establishment and operationalisation of the Genome EDIC, it is important to continue tapping into the expertise of the 1+MG UC communities to better tailor the offering to the evolving needs of the target group.

In order to help map the requirements for a sustainable 1+MG infrastructure and its governance model, the authors of the present deliverable organised virtual workshops in October 2025 with the experts from the following 1+MG UCs/1+MG WGs:

- 1+MG Use Case: Rare Diseases
- 1+MG Use Case: Cancer
- 1+MG Use Case Common complex diseases/pharmacogenomics
- 1+MG Use Case: Infectious Diseases
- 1+MG Use Case: Population Genomics

All leads, co-leads, and core members of the five 1+MG WGs were invited to participate in the UC workshops. The invitees were also encouraged to extend the invite to their colleagues and collaborators whom they believed would be suitable participants in the discussions.

¹³ European Commission *EU Funding & Tenders Portal* Accessed 22 November 2025 <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/projects-details/43152860/101194865/DIGITAL>

For convenience reasons, and to accommodate the scheduling constraints of the UC experts, a decision was made to combine use case discussions based on the thematic similarities and membership overlaps of the expert groups among the UCs. As a consequence, the five expert groups were convened in 3 virtual workshops held during October 2025. High-level information about the workshops is provided in the table below:

Table 1. Overview of Use Case Workshops organised in October 2025

N	Workshop date	1+MG Use Case(s) covered	Number of participants (incl. moderators)	Moderators
1	7 October 2025	Cancer, Rare Diseases	10	Regina Becker (LNDS)
2	16 October 2025	Population genomics, pharmacogenomics	8	Troels Rasmussen (NGC)
3	17 October 2025	Infectious diseases	7	Troels Rasmussen (NGC)

The 1+MG UC experts invited to the workshops were provided with preparatory materials. These included a background document describing the purpose of the workshops and an accompanying questionnaire collecting preliminary information about the experts' needs and requirements in terms of accessing/analysing genomic and related data. These preparatory materials are attached to the present deliverable in the annex.

The virtual workshops were moderated by Regina Becker, LNDS (Workshop 1) and Troels Rasmussen, NGC (Workshops 2 & 3). In order to streamline the workshops, the moderators followed a structured presentation format. The questionnaire that had been disseminated as part of the preparatory materials was used as an indicative guide to inform the flow of the conversations, although the moderators also allowed for significant deviations, where warranted, thus keeping the discussions open-ended to help elicit relevant insights. The workshops were video/audio-recorded to enable subsequent analysis. The workshops and their related communication exchanges resulted in three types of output:

- Invited experts' preliminary responses to the written questionnaire provided as part of the preparatory material
- The audio and video-recordings of the workshops
- The initial notes as well as more thematically structured minutes of the workshops (prepared by NGC colleagues)

This output was subsequently analysed by the research team of the lead beneficiary (LNDS). In order to effectively synthesise the insights and findings from the output material, inductive content analysis was carried out, a qualitative research methodology whereby themes and content categories are identified based on the collected qualitative data itself, as opposed to pre-defined.

5. Results

The analysis of the output from the three workshops and their related materials (i.e., questionnaires, meeting notes and minutes, and audio/video recordings) has generated findings that can be grouped under two broad themes: *needs of the 1+MG target community*, and *challenges to the realisation of the 1+MG vision*. Each of these broad themes were associated with multiple categories, as summarised in the table below. These categories were recurring topics across the workshops, discussed by multiple participants from different angles.

Table 2. Broad themes and their associated content categories identified as part of the 1+MG Use Case workshops organised in October 2025

Theme: Needs of the 1+MG target community	Theme: challenges to the realisation of the 1+MG vision
Content categories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Infrastructural needs ● Data-related needs ● Governance needs 	Content categories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Making 1+MG offering more attractive ● Rapidly changing technology ● Integration into the EHDS ● Articulating a robust sustainability strategy

The remaining sections of this chapter describes the insights collected along the themes and their related categories summarised in Table 2.

5.1. Needs of the 1+MG target community

The needs of the target community were discussed in relation to three different aspects of the 1+MG offering: the data processing infrastructure, the data itself (“the 1+MG Virtual Cohort”), and the data governance processes.

5.1.1. Infrastructural needs

Throughout the workshops, a clear consensus emerged that the data infrastructure to be operationalised in the framework of 1+MG should follow a federated topology with local (e.g., national or regional) storage and data processing capacity. Similarly, there was a unanimous agreement that this decentralised infrastructure should be operated under harmonised governance rules and processes to ensure cross-border interoperability.

Another conclusion met with broad consensus was that the infrastructure should strive to be flexible, i.e., modular in its ability to incorporate new components and replace old ones. This was deemed necessary to both meet the ever-changing needs of the target community, and to avoid “vendor lock-in”, i.e., over-reliance on the technical solutions of a specific technology provider, which would make the critical capabilities of the 1+MG infrastructure dependent on this provider. Also noticed by the moderators - many participants expressed needs that required the ability to bridge data and resources across different target communities highlighting the need for an agile approach driven by research missions - that is likely to bridge experts and data within a complex ecosystem.

Similarly, participants of all workshops have stressed the necessity of ensuring that the infrastructure can provide significant data storage capabilities, with one participant noting that the field of genomic research already generates more data than astrophysics (Workshop 1). However, another participant cautioned against indiscriminate retention of all data, stressing the need for data “exclusion criteria” based on the utility and quality of the data (Workshop 3). This was deemed necessary to ensure judicious use of the 1+MG data storage capacity, which could become significantly costly in the future, particularly with the addition of extensive phenotypic and multi-omic data. Ultimately, however, participants in all workshops agreed that the data storage specification will be informed by the forthcoming Genome EDIC’s data inclusion and quality criteria (discussed in the next sub-section).

According to the workshop participants, there can be significant differences in infrastructural needs depending on the context in which data are used. Specifically, uses for healthcare purposes, such as looking up similar patients to confirm a diagnosis, were deemed less computationally intensive. Participants believed that in most cases in the healthcare setting, genomic data could be in the gVCF format, with the information look-up taking place based on predefined, standardised workflows. The only difference was the infectious diseases expert group (Workshop 3), whose participants highlighted the importance of establishing linkages among many organisations connected to the local (e.g., national) node of the cross-border genomic infrastructure. According to one participant of this workshop, relevant data in the context of infectious diseases tends to be more scattered across different medical centres, such as GP practices, national or regional screening centres, various clinics where the patient may have sought ad-hoc diagnostic testing for a suspected infection or, in the case of affected patients, hospitals administering in-patient care. It was acknowledged that establishing such linkages would be challenging for the infrastructure to be overseen by

Genome EDIC. However, in the context of the remaining four 1+MG UCs, the infrastructural needs of the data use for healthcare purposes were deemed less demanding compared to the research context.

By contrast, participants anticipated greater infrastructural (including computational) needs when it came to enabling research use of the 1+MG data. This was mainly attributed to the more exploratory nature of research and hence a greater variety of the data analysis requests - some highly computationally intensive – expected from the researchers using the infrastructure. Importantly, the participants also discussed challenges in anticipating precise research questions that the end-users of the 1+MG infrastructure may want to pose in the future. However, the necessity of investing in the suitable infrastructural components was widely acknowledged, as this would determine the extent to which the 1+MG infrastructure could serve the research community. For example, during the first workshop, part of the discussion focused on the relative advantages and disadvantages of the different types of integrated circuits, such as FPGAs and ASICs. The participants in this workshop noted that whilst the former are generally superior for scaling up relatively streamlined bioinformatic workflows, the latter could be desirable to facilitate more novel or “exotic” types of bioinformatic analysis. Hence, the choice of the integrated circuits is inextricably linked to the nature of the data analysis Genome EDIC decides to offer to the researchers using its infrastructure (Workshop 1). As a constraining factor, the participants across all three workshops highlighted the significant uncertainty stemming from a rapidly changing technological landscape in genomic research, in conjunction with the limitations to their own understanding of the various ways in which genomic data infrastructures could meet the evolving needs of the research community.

Additional considerations were briefly discussed in relation to the potential utilisation of the 1+MG infrastructure and data collections in the context of policy-making and public health, such as population screening and prevention programs. Several participants noted that if the 1+MG resources were to be used for these purposes, the resultant data storage and computational requirements would be significant. However, it was also noted that currently, there is no clear roadmap for incorporating the 1+MG data and infrastructural resources into such national public health efforts. Moreover, participants in the three workshops also spoke about significant disparities across EU countries in genomics-based screening and prevention programs, questioning the feasibility of harmonised approaches across the countries participating in the 1+MG Initiative.

5.1.2. Data-related needs

As all three UC workshops involved the potential end-users of the 1+MG data, the topic of data-related needs was prominently discussed in the meetings.

All participants have highlighted the importance of having access to high-quality, rich phenotypic data, in addition to the genomic data. The participants acknowledged and

commended the effort of the 1+MG community towards defining the harmonised minimal 1+MG data model (that is, minimum categories/variables of data a dataset must cover, as well as the data quality criteria, for the dataset to be eligible for inclusion into the 1+MG virtual cohort). However, the participants also pointed out the deficiencies of the existing 1+MG harmonised minimal data model. For example, participants in Workshop 1 highlighted that the 1+MG minimum requirements, as defined currently, don't cover several important data types, such as: multi-omic (e.g., methylation, RNA) data, phenotypic information such as clinical outcomes, relevant medical diagnoses among the patient's immediate ancestors, as well as data on lifestyle and environmental factors. Another limitation that came up in all three workshops was the lack of longitudinal data which the workshop participants deemed particularly useful for healthcare uses of the 1+MG virtual cohort.

Harmonisation of data was seen as an important element. The minimum dataset should be fully harmonised; ideally also more data. This is relevant for data findability to start with.

Another important requirement that was voiced in relation to the data was that the data in the 1+MG virtual cohort must be representative of the European population, and the quality of the data should be comparable (meaning, having been collected following similar protocols/procedures). However, the participants were aware of the diverging procedures and practices across genomic data collection centres, ranging from patient/research participant inclusion criteria to different SOPs and dissimilar data quality metrics.

5.1.3. Governance needs

Unlike the past discussions of 1+MG UCs organised as part of other projects (e.g., UC workshops carried out during the B1MG project in 2020-2022), the governance of the 1+MG data and infrastructure was not the main focus of the October 2025 UC workshops reported in this document. Nevertheless, several considerations concerning the data access/use governance were raised by the participants.

Most pertinently, workshop participants emphasised the importance of obtaining access to the requested data within a reasonable timeframe, which would vary depending on the context of the intended data use. In particular, data access and use for healthcare purposes was deemed more time-sensitive, necessitating an access decision in a matter of days. Participants pointed out that in the healthcare context, medical professionals in several EU countries are able to access local (institutional and/or national) healthcare registries where they can look up genomic and phenotypic data relating to patients similar to their own. However, according to the workshop participants, no such possibility exists for clinicians seeking access to similar data from other countries in Europe. Facilitating such cross-border access for healthcare purposes was considered an important potential added value of the Genome EDIC's offering to the community.

With regards to the research context, participants acknowledged that deciding on access requests generally takes longer, while requestors are also typically asked to provide a more extensive supporting documentation before their request can be granted. Nevertheless, the participants expressed their frustrations over the unduly lengthy access procedures that, in practice, can easily take more than a year where data access is requested for research purposes. Importantly, the new data access workflows outlined in the EHDS Regulation were not seen as a major improvement, considering that under the EHDS Regulation timeframes, provision of data access can take up to a year (3 months with a possible 3 month extension to review and approve the access request by the relevant Health Data Access Body; up to another 6 months for preparing and providing data to the user in the Secure Processing Environment). As a consequence, the workshop participants expressed their hope that Genome EDIC can help facilitate access to the 1+MG virtual cohort data for research purposes under a shorter timeframe.

5.2. Challenges

The exploration of the infrastructural, data analysis, and governance needs of the 1+MG target audience was dovetailed by discussions revolving around the challenges facing the 1+MG initiative. These challenges can be delineated into the following categories:

- Making the 1+MG offering more attractive to the relevant stakeholders
- Uncertainties created by the rapidly evolving technological landscape
- Integration of the 1+MG infrastructure into the EHDS ecosystem
- Articulation of a robust sustainability strategy, including viable business models

5.2.1 Making 1+MG offering more attractive

The most pronounced challenge, discussed extensively throughout all the workshops, was difficulties in making the 1+MG offering more attractive to the large number of relevant stakeholders. In this regard, three directions have emerged, each aimed at meeting the needs of different stakeholder groups:

- identifying new use cases for the 1+MG virtual cohort and the infrastructure;
- convincing policy-makers of the utility of the 1+MG offering to accelerate adoption in the public health context;
- fine-tuning the offering to the known target groups in order to better meet their real needs

In terms of identifying new use cases for the forthcoming 1+MG European virtual cohort and the supporting 1+MG data infrastructure, the discussions mainly revolved around finding ways to support clinical trial recruitment and other forms of medicinal product development. The participants noted that as the 1+MG initiative gradually builds its genomic data collections and associated rich phenotypic data across Europe, it will create a valuable resource for the biotechnology and pharmaceutical industries. Consequently, it would be worthwhile to explore the possibility of developing services and support capabilities geared

towards industry users. This could include, for example, aiding sponsors of clinical trials in recruiting suitable participants based on pharmacogenomic profile, particularly where the efficacy of the investigational drug is suspected to be influenced by genetic factors (Workshop 2). The 1+MG virtual cohort could also be used to support validation of findings in a trial, provided the datasets constituting the 1+MG virtual cohort include the requisite data of sufficient quality to support such validation.

Apart from identifying new use cases, the participants of the three workshops also discussed the necessity of demonstrating the utility of 1+MG in the context of public health. Although policy-making is among the known secondary uses of 1+MG data with its dedicated governance framework, the participants of the workshop felt that presently, there is insufficient interest among the target audience for this application. In particular, the moderator of the second and third workshops spoke of the necessity for compelling health economic analyses, aimed at demonstrating the net benefits of genomics-informed population screening, prevention, and other public health programs. Other participants in all three workshops contributed to the discussion by highlighting diverging public health priorities across the EU Member States involved in the 1+MG Initiative. This led to the conclusion that efforts aimed at convincing policymakers would likely result in varying degrees of success across the countries. Nevertheless, it was emphasised that an ongoing dialogue with this stakeholder group is critically important, as this group plays a key role in their country's continuous commitment to the successful implementation of the 1+MG vision. Some participants (Workshop 2) have suggested using pharmacogenomics to initiate or sustain such dialogues with policy-makers. Based on the insights from the national implementation of pharmacogenomics into the healthcare context in their country, one participant noted that virtually 100% of the general population has at least one variant of pharmacogenomic relevance. This observation, the participants of the workshop argued, makes pharmacogenomics a “low-hanging fruit” when engaging policy-makers, enabling the 1+MG community to demonstrate benefits of genomics-informed public health programs.

Finally, a substantial part of the discussion focused on identifying and meeting more specific needs of the known target groups, especially the researchers. Whilst the participants of the three workshops offered their general thoughts concerning the various requirements of the broader research community (as summarised in the previous sub-section), they also felt that a more granular discussion of specific infrastructural and data needs was warranted. Several participants cautioned against designing infrastructural components without duly consulting the target audience of researchers, primarily bioinformaticians, and data scientists. In the words of one participant, the developers of the infrastructure should avoid “telling the researchers what they [researchers] need, but [provide them] with an agnostic platform” that meets the requirements of a broad set of research projects. This sentiment was also echoed by the workshop moderators. However, noting that resource constraints would likely prevent the infrastructure from serving the needs of all possible research projects, the moderators spoke of the need to identify and prioritise the more impactful potential

research uses of the 1+MG infrastructure and the virtual cohort. There was a consensus that such prioritisation must be informed by the input provided by the researchers themselves.

5.2.2. Rapidly changing technology

Interestingly, the discussion around the necessity of mapping infrastructural requirements at a more granular level was accompanied by the acknowledgment that rapidly advancing technology makes it difficult to accurately anticipate the nature of genomics-focused research projects several years into the future. One participant (Workshop 1) pointed out that certain categories of data-driven research, such as multi-omic studies and analyses integrating long-read sequencing data, while increasingly commonplace today, were hard to anticipate in the past years. Based on this experience, the participant expressed significant uncertainty about their ability to accurately predict the infrastructural and computing needs of researchers in the future, especially where the planning horizon is 5-10 years or longer. The same general consideration was articulated with respect to the data-related needs of the future end-users of 1+MG virtual cohort. This, according to the participants, necessitates periodic revisiting and refinement of 1+MG data inclusion and data quality requirements. Considering the potentially significant storage costs of the extended phenotypic, genomic (particularly if stored in non-compressed data formats for research purposes) and multi-omic data, the participants felt it would be prudent to periodically reassess whether continuous retention of the data is still warranted. In one workshop, the moderator noted that the participants were not concerned or aware of the data sharing problems associated with new processing tools and services - specifically the roll-out of Illumina DRAGEN processing unit, which uses proprietary software, effectively requiring the data to be realigned on CPU based servers to make these data harmonized according to 1+MG standards.

5.2.3. Integration into the EHDS

All the participants were aware of the recently adopted EHDS Regulation and acknowledged the forthcoming EHDS ecosystem as the new reality. Although exploring the potential interactions between the 1+MG and the EHDS was not the focus of the workshops, the participants felt that the EHDS has increased the complexity of the 1+MG governance discussions. In their introductory remarks, the workshop moderators highlighted the importance of synergising, complementing, or aligning with the EHDS, pointing out that significant work along these lines is underway.

The topic of aligning with the EHDS was notably raised by participants in two contexts: i) in reference to access to genomic and associated phenotypic data, where the participants felt 1+MG could deliver expedited access provision compared to the EHDS timeframes, and ii) regarding possible incorporation of additional clinical data (including longitudinal clinical data) into the 1+MG-enabled data analysis, where participants felt there was potential for the 1+MG infrastructure to leverage the secondary use pathways through the EHDS. Overall, the participants agreed that continued exploration of interactions between 1+MG and the

EHDS is a worthwhile endeavour and welcomed the work of the 1+MG ELSI community along these lines.

5.2.4 Articulation of a robust sustainability strategy

The challenges to the 1+MG implementation were perceived as a limiting factor to the elaboration of a robust sustainability strategy, including potential business models to be adopted by the forthcoming Genome EDIC. The participants acknowledged the unique challenges of 1+MG sustainability stemming largely from both the multi-country establishment of the infrastructure, and the multi-user nature of its offering.

Nevertheless, the participants noted that the sustainability-focused work of the 1+MG community would benefit from the experience of other organisations overseeing large biomedical data collections, provided that the differences and unique characteristics of Genome EDIC are duly acknowledged. For example, sustainability-related discussion in Workshop 3 drew parallels between the forthcoming Genome EDIC and the UK Biobank. According to one participant, Genome EDIC could consider entering in institutional subscription-based agreements with research universities – an approach adopted by the UK Biobank – whereby individual researchers from the institute could access the data for a predefined fee billed from their personal account and get subsequently reimbursed by their institute. However, the participant also noted that the approach would likely not work for accessing and using the 1+MG data for healthcare purposes, where the pricing model would need to be tailored to the healthcare reimbursement system of the country in question.

Most crucially, the participants agreed that determination of the business model would need to be preceded by a more detailed understanding of the offer provided by Genome EDIC.

6. Discussion, Conclusions and Next steps

The three 1+MG UC workshops organised by the co-leads of B1MGplus WP2 (“Genome EDIC establishment”) in October 2025 have resulted in valuable insights for informing the sustainability-related work of the B1MGplus consortium.

One of the key takeaways from the workshops was the importance of continuous stakeholder engagement. An important objective of stakeholder engagement efforts would be to demonstrate the value of 1+MG via key stakeholders such as public health authorities and policy-makers. According to the workshop participants, this could be accomplished by emphasising high-utility applications of genomics in the public health context, such as pharmacogenomics. Another key objective should be mapping more granular technical requirements for the 1+MG infrastructure and the data. This may require the involvement of a larger group of bioinformaticians and data scientists whose valuable insights could help

elicit more detailed specifications. However, the 1+MG community should be mindful of the rapidly changing technological paradigms, which might render such technical and data-related requirements obsolete in a matter of a few years. Consequently, it would be judicious to ensure that the implementation of the requirements from future discussions can be finalised within a reasonable timeframe following the requirements' elicitation.

A pronounced finding of the workshops was a strong demand for data availability through the forthcoming 1+MG virtual cohort. Participants discussed at length the end-users' need for more, better-quality, and multi-modal data, preferably collected longitudinally. From the point of view of Genome EDIC, these requirements could be operationalised in the form of more extensive and strictly enforced data inclusion as well as data quality criteria.¹⁴ However, there is a risk that this approach may result in the exclusion of sizable potentially valuable datasets that already exist across Europe. The decision by the forthcoming Genome EDIC about dataset inclusion/exclusion needs to be based on balancing the stated requirements of the end-users against the quality and content of the available datasets across the EU. At the same time, more extended data collection and quality criteria could be used as requirements for future genome-sequencing efforts that are funded by the European Commission, where the explicit aim is to bring the generated datasets under the 1+MG governance framework. Early Europe-wide genome-sequencing efforts of such nature are currently underway, with the Genome of Europe (GoE) project being the prime example. The objectives of the GoE project include collecting and making available for reuse approximately 100 000 genomes that are representative of the European population.¹⁵ Having commenced in October 2024, GoE's start significantly predates both the establishment of Genome EDIC and the Genome EDIC's formal adoption of the 1+MG data and quality criteria. Therefore, the feasibility of ensuring that GoE's data collections meet the data inclusion and quality criteria of Genome EDIC is currently uncertain. However, future genome-sequencing efforts funded by the European Commission could come with a formal requirement that data-collection efforts must comply with the data inclusion and quality criteria formally adopted by Genome EDIC.

Importantly, the conversations with the 1+MG UC leads have indirectly led to the elicitation of some potential roles to be tackled by the forthcoming Genome EDIC. This could include operationalising new use cases, in alignment with the EDIC's sustainability strategy. For example, dedicated services for a new use case tailored to the industry needs could be offered, if indicated by the EDIC's sustainability strategy. Another important potential role of Genome EDIC, based on the workshops, could be active involvement in data quality curation, alongside continuous monitoring and reassessment of data inclusion/exclusion criteria. These considerations will be important in the coming months, as the exact scope of Genome EDIC is defined and translated into the formal policies and statutes of the forthcoming legal entity.

¹⁴ For the current definition of the GDI/1+MG Minimal Data Model, see <https://health-ri.github.io/HarmonisedMinimalDatamodel/> (Accessed 23 November 2025)

¹⁵ Genome of Europe: "About Us" page. <https://genomeofeurope.eu/about/>

Finally, continuous assessment of the complex interplay between the EHDS and the 1+MG Infrastructure/governance is going to be an important workstream for the 1+MG community in the years ahead. The assessment should focus on the compatibility, complementarity, and synergies between the two infrastructures and their respective governance frameworks. Importantly, significant work along these lines has been completed by the 1+MG ELSI community, dating back to the B1MG project (2020-2023), where the preliminary output of the analysis was incorporated into the compilation B1MG deliverable D2.4. ("Report on data access and governance framework").¹⁶ With the subsequent evolution and ongoing deployment of the EHDS, this work by the 1+MG ELSI community is currently ongoing and will further accelerate across various projects.

ANNEX 1. Proposed 1+MG Use Case workshops on principal user needs - set up and questions

Motivation

5 workshops have been proposed, one for each current focus area in the 1+MG initiative (Cancer; Common diseases; Rare diseases; Infectious diseases; Pharmacogenetics). These workshops will help 1+MG and its implementation projects to define a business model for its human genomics infrastructure. This model will be based on the specific needs of its prospective users, the initial scale of the operations, and the path towards scaleup in the future. The workshops will be set up in a similar manner to those organised in 2020, which were instrumental in defining the data governance framework for the infrastructure.

The objective of these workshops is twofold. Firstly, the workshops will seek to identify the research and healthcare-related questions that users could address within the 1+MG infrastructure. Secondly, they will establish the requirements for the infrastructure to support users' missions. Which critical infrastructure and data elements can support researchers and clinicians in their work? What would be the impact if the infrastructure improved on the status quo? Are there questions or use cases that are currently unanswerable? Are there any frequent problems or research questions that cannot be addressed satisfactorily? Which research questions could potentially be addressed more efficiently (e.g., faster, better quality through higher statistics)? The answers to these questions will help to better understand the user needs and take careful and strategic decisions on quality and service parameters to design the infrastructure and prioritise implementation tracks.

These workshops are integral to the development of our product and service portfolio, as well as the creation of a coherent business model and longterm sustainability work.

¹⁶ B1MG Deliverable 2.4 *Report on Data Access and Governance Framework* <https://zenodo.org/records/8411102> (Note that this deliverable analysed the interplay between 1+MG and EHDS based on an earlier version of the EHDS Regulation text, from March 2022. The legislative proposal subsequently underwent significant modifications before being voted into law. More recent analyses by the 1+MG ELSI community are available upon request.

Long-term sustainability comes from a clear and solid business model.¹ All business models are based on the ability to link the three elements of the business model triangle: WHAT service do we offer? HOW do we do that? WHY does that bring value? But also, to WHOM? At this point, we have a general idea of WHAT and HOW - we are still very generic in our approach to WHO our services are targeted - and WHY that would bring value to them? These workshops will be focused on end-users (WHO), with different needs (WHAT), requiring different support(HOW), in order to create value (WHY). The objective of these workshops is to facilitate a discussion and investigation with potential user communities to ascertain their requirements and needs, thereby enabling us to refine our services and value creation processes.

Background: B1MGplus

The B1MGplus consortium supports the scaling up and sustainability considerations of the 1+MG initiative, building upon and support the current ([GDI](#) and [GoE](#)) and past projects ([B1MG](#)).² WP2 of the B1MGplus project is dedicated to the creation of the EDIC. The role of Task 2.4 in this work package is to support the GDI project's sustainability considerations by providing relevant information to help tailor the infrastructure towards user needs and come up with sustainable business models for the initial and subsequent development of the infrastructure.

B1MGplus has several objectives:

- Support the sustainability and scale up of 1+MG by providing input and relevant background information for the design of a federated European data infrastructure for the advancement of genomic healthcare and research based on a European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC), which is largely driving the planned workshop.
- Facilitate the uptake of genomics into healthcare delivery and public health policy and developing the guidelines for meta-data standards and data quality assurance within the 1+MG Framework.

1 + MG User Journey

The intention of 1+MG is to make genomic and phenotypic / clinical data available through a harmonised data governance. Datasets included have to comply with minimum dataset requirements that depend on the context in which the data are collected. Please find the [link to the 1+MG minimum data models](#).

Ideally, the 1+MG data collection should be as uniform as possible, and include minimal metadata standards attached to them, in order to be scientifically valuable. Therefore requirements will be made with regard to data harmonisation (at least the mandatory items within the minimum dataset variables must be harmonised) as well as requirements regarding the quality and accuracy of the data. (more information can be found in [the folder of the GDI-WP6 Milestone 24: Workshop on best practice on maximizing data quality and utility when preparing data for inclusion into the infrastructure](#))

The 1+MG infrastructure should facilitate the discovery of data from data catalogues with aggregated information on different datasets, but it should also enable the discovery of data

subjects with certain genotype / phenotype / clinical information to which an access request could be submitted.

If an access request is approved, data would be made available in a federated interoperable network of secure processing environments (SPEs) where the data reside. However, if a project cannot be pursued in a federated setup, data could also be pooled in one of these SPEs (subject to the agreement of country / 1+MG data holder for such scheme).

Only aggregated non-personal data can be exported from the SPEs. Personal data will remain in the 1+MG infrastructure and are archived to be available for reproducibility purposes.

Workshops to understand user needs

The plan is to organise workshops with the 1+MG Use Case Working Groups to better understand user needs in terms of scope and frequency. This knowledge is required in order to define the business model of the infrastructure and to assist with the description of the implementation phase expected as part of the EDIC application. Depending on their requirements, users will need data of a certain comprehensiveness, whether in terms of data types or the number of datasets, cross-border access (i.e. the ability to access data from several other countries for representation or sheer quantity), harmonisation requirements, compute capacity requirements or other requirements for the computing environment. The infrastructure cannot implement everything users request immediately, so it is necessary to understand whether certain demands are rare cases or regular needs, whether the infrastructure can improve current practices, and whether questions that were previously not reasonably possible can now be addressed. As part of the sustainability considerations, a roadmap for the implementation of features will be developed.

With this in mind, and in order to help create a coherent infrastructure for genomic data and accompanying health and other relevant data so as to provide a more assertive and evidence-based diagnostics, treatment, prevention, care, quality management, policy-making and innovation in healthcare; we plan to hold several Use Case Workshops to better understand user needs and assess the future costs and complexity.

These Use Case Workshops will be focused on the five different areas currently covered in 1+MG:

- Rare diseases
- Cancer³
- Population genomics
- Infectious diseases, including Covid-19
- Pharmacogenomics

The questions will be organised into different sets, each covering a specific category:

- General questions which are independent of the more specific type of data use
- Questions related to use-case specific requirements for data characteristics, origin and use
- Questions related to use-case specific technical needs

Specific Use Cases

The needs will likely vary depending on the domain. Therefore, it might be important to differentiate between usage of the infrastructure in research and healthcare for which access to the 1+MG infrastructure would be sought beyond just disease groups:

- Clinical research
- Biomedical research
- Bioinformatics research
- Clinical decision making

Ideally, there would be at least one typical example of a practical research or healthcare reuse project in each field of the 1+MG Use Case Working Groups that would benefit from the 1+MG infrastructure. The idea is that the 1+MG Use Case Working Groups could prepare for the workshop(s) in advance based on the questions below. This would be similar to the use case workshops that we held in 2020 to understand the user needs to come up with a data governance. We now need additional information to plan the minimum setup and potential upgrades of the infrastructure.

The following questions are proposed to be addressed in the workshops:

Giving tangible examples

Please describe briefly different representative examples for a practical project in your field that would benefit from the 1+MG infrastructure. The description should ideally cover the question to be answered, the data needs and the compute needs.

- *Easy = no advanced compute infrastructure needed; standard software tools, no complex datasets with lots of variables, data operations, can easily be done in a federated compute environment*
- *Medium complex = advanced compute infrastructure may be needed but with standard software; or own software is run but on nothing too complicated; (i.e., some steps up from the “easy” setup but not too many challenges)*
- *Challenging = likely advanced software needed, also complex own software; training of AI models may fall into this section; complex datasets; likely advanced computer infrastructure needed; could be difficult to pursue in a federated compute environment.*

An example could look like this:

Characterizing cancer genomes for patterns of somatic retrotransposition (e.g. LINE-1 mediated SV)⁴

- **Purpose and setting:** *Finding the role of a specific transposable element (TE) in remodelling the architecture of the cancer genome in a particular tumour. E.g. among Long interspersed nuclear element 1 (L1) mediated structural variations (SV) we can list: direct insertion, L1 mediated double strand breaks (DSB) and formation of Mb-large deletions that, occasionally, promote cancer development through the removal of tumor-suppressor genes or the amplification of oncogenes.*
- **Questions**
To tell if L1 polymorphisms can be a relevant source of structural variants associated with a certain tumor risks we can check if:

- Are there matching events between data of the research group (so data outside 1+MG) and 1+MG data (are somatic retrotransposition events found in our samples present in other samples)?
- Are matching events tumour specific?
- Are matching events population specific (cross talk with GnomAD SV, L1db, and dbRIP) ?
- What is the frequency of the events in the overall analyzed population?
- What is the allelic frequency in tumour samples if compared with normal samples?
- **Types of data needed from 1+MG**
 - Genomic data: WGS, targeted (panel) sequencing
 - Genotype data of structural variants (SVs) of different individuals from different populations
 - Clinical data: diagnosis, stage, grade, therapy, ethnicity/ancestry.
 - (Search across the entire 1+MG collection)
- **Data analysis**
 - Use of existing software tools (tbc) (which ones?)
 - [Data requests \(statistical/aggregated answers\) versus analysis that require a permit \(links nicely to EHDS\)](#)
 - Federated analysis is possible
 - HPC is needed (tbc)
 - One time analysis (shorter timeframe) versus successive sequential and/or parallel analysis to come to a result (that can take an entire PhD trajectory)

General Questions

1. If we could only serve easy cases, or, alternatively, easy and medium complex cases:
What percentage of projects could be served by the 1+MG infrastructure? Should differences be made per type of project (clinical research, biomedical research, bioinformatics research, clinical decision-making)?
2. Which features of 1+MG are the most important?
Of the following list of 1+MG provided features, which can you already use, which could improve your current situation, and which would offer new possibilities?
 - a. Availability of data across many EU Member States
 - b. Availability of data from healthcare including treatment and outcome information
 - c. Availability of data from research
 - d. Detailed metadata for data findability
 - e. Findability of special patient profiles across different collections / providers
 - f. Accessibility of data from different sources through a single access request
 - g. Fast response times on access requests

- e. *What would be your reasons to pursue a subject-level data discovery? How likely is it that you need this for the different types of your projects?*
- f. *Is the minimum dataset sufficient for subject-level data discovery? Would all clinical / phenotypic data in the minimum data model be needed for subject-level data discovery?*
6. *Will you need to bring in your own data? Size, format? Could you give an estimate how often that is the case depending on the type and/or complexity of your projects?*
7. *Which data must be harmonised for your projects (e.g. to find the data in the first place) and cannot be harmonised during your use?*

Technical Needs:

1. *The 1+MG infrastructure will make tools and software available in its SPEs, but it will also allow users to bring in their own software.*
 - a. *Which standard tools would you need / expect to be available on the platform?*
 - b. *How often do you expect to use non-standard tools / software for the different project types / complexities? What kind would these be?*
 - c. *How often do you expect to use your own bespoke tools / software for the different types / complexity of projects?*
2. *1+MG will have to plan its provision of compute platforms, in particular advanced computing with relevant features.*
 - a. *What are the typical computing needs of your projects? (e.g. fast input/output; big memory; large number of FLOPs, other...)*
 - b. *Which platforms do you need or would you like to use?*
 - c. *What is the typical "volume" of the entire dataset needed? (to get a picture for network bandwidth, storage demands, ..)*
 - d. *What is the time frame for job execution? [platform-d*

